

Effectiveness of Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol on Corneal Complications among Patients with Mechanical Ventilation at Selected Tertiary Care Hospital, Puducherry – A Randomized Controlled Trial.

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Abstract

Introduction: In intensive care units (ICUs), patients who are paralysed or under anaesthesia frequently experience ocular surface problems. Treatment in ICUs typically focuses on managing organ failures, making eye care a secondary concern. Ophthalmological problems therefore do arise (incidence ranging from 3.6% to 60%) but are typically disregarded in this situation. The objectives of the study were to evaluate the effectiveness of comprehensive eye care protocol on corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A Quantitative research approach of randomized controlled trial with two group pre and post – test designs were adopted for this study. A total of 66 subjects had been recruited using the purposive sampling technique and 33 subjects each for the experimental and control group had been randomly assigned. Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol (CECP) was given to the experimental group whereas control group participants were on routine care. Data were collected using structured instruments that included socio-demographic and clinical variables, Assessment of Severity of Corneal Complications to assess the corneal complications. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 21. **RESULTS:** There was a statistically significant difference on comparison of severity of corneal complications between experimental and control group at level $p < 0.05$. **CONCLUSION:** Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol is proved to be effective in improving the comprehensive eye care protocol on corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation.

KEYWORDS: Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol (CECP), Assessment, Corneal complications.

Introduction:

In intensive care units (ICUs), patients who are paralysed or under anaesthesia frequently experience ocular surface problems. Treatment in ICUs typically focuses on managing organ failures, making eye care a secondary concern. Ophthalmological problems therefore do arise (incidence ranging from 3.6% to 60%) but are typically disregarded in this situation. To determine the greatest evidence currently on hand for offering the best eye care to ward off exposure keratopathy. Microbial keratitis and vision loss can be avoided with early diagnosis and effective treatment^[2].

Reviews of numerous research revealed that there are few procedures for eye care in patients in special wards who are hospitalized, the impact of various treatments has not been adequately established, and clinical trials have produced inconsistent results. Determining a new eye care strategy to avoid ocular surface problems in hospitalized patients in the intensive care unit was the goal of this study. Hence the investigator aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of comprehensive eye care protocol on corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation^[3].

Materials and Methods

Design and setting

Using a randomized controlled trial design, data were collected from critical care units for 7 weeks (May – June 2023) from a tertiary care hospital in the private health sector of South India

Sample Size and Sampling

Participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique. The sample size was estimated using the formula for the comparison of two independent means. The sample size was estimated to be 33 in each group. The inclusion criteria consist of patient with Mechanical ventilation admitted at critical care unit, Patient who had sluggish blinking reflexes, patient with more than 30 years of age. The exclusion criteria consist of Patient whose attenders were not willing to give consent form for procedure to the participant.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

After obtaining validity of the tools from the experts belonging to the departments of Medical-Surgical Nursing, ophthalmology a pilot study was conducted among 10 samples patient with mechanical ventilation in critical care unit at MGMCRI for a period of 10 days from 24th April 2023 to 3rd May 2023.

The obtained reliability score was $r = 0.897$ for assessment of severity of corneal complications and for **CECP (Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol)**, $r = 0.912$ which indicated the tool was reliable and feasible. No further changes were made in the tool after pilot study.

DATA COLLECTION:

After obtaining informed consent, the data were collected using structured instruments that included socio-demographic and clinical variables, observation checklist used to assessment of severity of corneal complications in pre-test for both the groups. The score for the assessment of severity of corneal complications was categorized as no risk (0), mild risk (1-2), moderate risk (3-5), high risk (6-8).

Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol – compression of warm saline using eye care sponge for every 5 minutes dip into warm water and apply to the both the eyes over 30 minutes. Instill Lubrex eye drops of each eye 2 drops. Along with routine care. Taping the eyes and which was given by the investigator.

Control group participants on the other hand were on routine care. Post-test was done on 5th and 7th day to the assessment of severity of corneal complications among experimental and control group participants. The data were collected in the critical care unit of tertiary care hospital for 7 weeks.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 21. Frequency, Percentage distribution, Mean, Standard deviation on Distribution of demographic and clinical variables among experimental and control group. Friedman test on Comparison of pre and post-test on severity of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation within experimental and control group. Mann-Whitney Test on Comparison of pre and post-test severity of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation between experimental and control group. Chi –square test (X^2) on Association of selected demographic and clinical

variables with severity of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation in post-test among experimental and control group.

Table 1: Distribution of the demographic variables among patients with mechanical ventilation in experimental and control group. N = 66

S.No	Demographic variables	Experimental group (n=33)		Control group (n=33)	
		F	P	F	P
1	Age in years				
	a) 41-50 years	10	30.3	17	51.5
	b) 51-60 years	8	24.2	8	24.2
	c) Above 60 years	15	45.5	8	24.2
2	Gender				
	a) Male	24	72.7	27	81.8
	b) Female	9	27.3	6	18.2

Table 2: Distribution of the clinical variables on corneal complication among patients with mechanical ventilation in experimental and control group **N = 66**

S.No	Clinical variables	Experimental group (n=33)		Control group (n=33)	
		F	P	F	P
1.	Body mass index (BMI) in Kg/m²				
	a. 18.5-24.9 (Healthy weight)	0	0.0	1	3.0
	b. 25-29.9 (Overweight)	19	57.6	17	51.5
	c. >30(Obesity)	14	42.4	15	45.5
2.	Co-morbidities				
	No	17	51.5	21	63.6
	Yes	16	48.5	11	33.3
	If yes, specify	0	0.0	1	3.0
	a. Cardiac disease				
	No	20	60.6	26	78.8
	Yes	13	39.4	7	21.2
	b. Type II diabetes mellitus				
	No	21	63.6	25	75.8
	Yes	12	36.4	8	24.2
	c. Thyroid disorder				
	No	32	97.0	33	100.0
	Yes	1	3.0	0	0.0
	d. Respiratory disease				
	No	33	100.0	33	100.0
	e. Renal disease				

	No	32	97.0	32	97.0
	Yes	1	3.0	1	3.0
3.	Days on ventilator				
	a) 4-7days	24	72.7	28	84.8
	b) 8-10 days	9	27.3	5	15.2
4.	Glasgow coma scale				
	a) Coma	0	0.0	1	3.0
	b) Semicoma	11	33.3	4	12.1
	c) Stupor	22	66.7	28	84.8
5.	Diagnosis				
	a) Cardiovascular disease	6	18.2	14	42.4
	b) Respiratory disorder	7	21.2	2	6.1
	c) Neurological disorder	19	57.6	13	39.4
	d) Multiorgan dysfunction syndrome	1	3.0	1	3.0
	e) Renal disease	0	0.0	3	9.1
6.	Patient on treatment with drugs which increases the risk of ocular surface lesions				
	No	17	51.5	22	66.7
	Yes	16	48.5	11	33.3
	a) Metformin				
	No	21	63.6	25	75.8
	Yes	12	36.4	8	24.2
	b) Metoprolol				
	No	25	75.8	28	84.8
	Yes	8	24.2	5	15.2

	c) Telmisartan				
	No	31	93.9	32	97.0
	Yes	2	6.1	1	3.0
	d) Aspirin				
	No	31	93.9	32	97.0
	Yes	2	6.1	1	3.0
	e) Atorvastatin				
	No	32	97.0	32	97.0
	Yes	1	3.0	1	3.0
	f) Amlodipine				
	No	30	90.9	32	97.0
	Yes	3	9.1	1	3.0
	g) Dytor				
	No	33	100.0	33	100.0
7.	White blood cell count				
	a) Less than 4000 cells/cu.mm	1	3.0	4	12.1
	b) 4000-11000cells/cu. mm	19	57.6	20	60.6
	c) More than 11000cells/cu. mm	13	39.4	9	27.3

Table 3: Distribution of severity of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation in experimental group and control group during pre-test, post test-1 and post test-2 **N=66**

Severity of corneal complications	Pre test				Post test-1				Post test-2			
	Experimental group (n=33)		Control group (n=33)		Experimental group (n=33)		Control group (n=33)		Experimental group (n=33)		Control group (n=33)	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
NO RISK (0)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	9	27.3	8	24.2
MILD (1 - 2)	7	21.2	5	15.2	10	30.3	7	21.2	24	72.7	17	51.5
MODERATE (3 - 5)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
SEVERE (6 - 8)	26	78.8	28	84.8	23	69.7	26	78.8	0	0.0	8	24.2

Table 4: Comparison of severity of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation within experimental and control group **N=66**

Group	Observation	Mean	Median	Standard deviation	Friedman test	p- value
Experimental group	Pre test	3.06	3	0.70	62.000	<0.001 ^{***}
	Post test-1	2.79	3	1.05		
	Post test-2	1.00	1	0.75		
Control group	Pre test	3.03	3	0.59	47.185	<0.001 ^{***}
	Post test-1	2.85	3	0.87		
	Post test-2	1.45	1	1.12		

******* $p < 0.001$: highly statistically significant (HSS)

Hence the stated hypothesis H_1 that “There is a significant difference in the corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation those who had been subjected to Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol (CECP) than those who do not”.

Table 5: Comparison of severity of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation between experimental and control group. N=66

Observation	Experimental group	Control group	Mann – whitney test	P - value
	Mean	Mean		
Pre test	3.06	3.03	529.5	0.827
Post test-1	2.79	2.85	542	0.972
Post test-2	1.00	1.85	446.5	0.057

p>0.05-non significant (NS).

In post test-2 is statistically significant at level $p<0.05$. Hence the stated hypothesis H_1 that there is a significant difference in the corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation those who had been subjected to Comprehensive Eye Care Protocol (CECP) than those who do not is accepted”.

Table 6: Association of severity of corneal complications with selected demographic variables in experimental group. N=33

S.No	Demographic Variables	Corneal complications				Chi-square value(X^2)	p-value
		Experimental group					
		F	No risk	F	Mild		
1.	Age in years						1.7 (NS)
	a. 41-50 Years	4	44.40	6	25.00		
	b. 51-60Years	1	11.10	7	29.20		
	c. Above 60 Years	4	44.40	11	45.80		
2.	Gender						0.159 (NS)
	a. Male	7	77.80	17	70.80		
	b. Female	2	22.20	7	29.20		

p>0.05-non significant (NS).

Table 6 depicts that, demographic variables had not shown statistically significant association of severity of corneal complications in experimental group.

Table 7: Association of severity of corneal complications among mechanically ventilated patients with selected clinical variables in experimental group. N=33

S.No	Clinical Variables	Corneal complications				Chi-square value(X ²)	p-value
		Experimental group					
		F	No risk(P)	F	Mild(P)		
1.	Body mass index (BMI) in kg/m²						
	a. 25-29.9 (Overweight)	6	66.70	13	54.20	0.419	0.518 (NS)
	b. More than 30 (Obesity)	3	33.30	11	45.80		
2.	Co-morbidities						
	No	5	55.60	12	50.00	0.081	0.776 (NS)
	Yes	4	44.40	12	50.00		
	a. Cardiac disease						
	No	6	66.70	14	58.30	0.19	0.663 (NS)
	Yes	3	33.30	10	41.70		
	b. Type II diabetes mellitus						
	No	5	55.60	16	66.70	0.349	0.555
	Yes	4	44.40	8	33.30		

							(NS)
	c. Thyroid disorder						
	No	8	88.90	24	100.00	2.75	0.097 (NS)
	Yes	1	11.10	0	0.00		
	d. Renal disease						
	No	9	100.00	23	95.80	0.387	0.534 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.00	1	4.20		
3.	Days on ventilator support						
	a. 4-7days	6	66.70	18	75.00	0.229	0.632 (NS)
	b. 8-10days	3	33.30	6	25.00		
4.	Glasgow coma scale						
	a. Semicoma	3	33.30	8	33.30	0	1.000 (NS)
	b. Stupor	6	66.70	16	66.70		
5.	Diagnosis						
	a. Cardiovascular disease	1	11.10	5	20.80	0.899	0.826 (NS)
	b. Respiratory disease	2	22.20	5	20.80		
	c. Neurological disease	6	66.70	13	54.20		
	d. Multi organ dysfunction syndrome	0	0.00	1	4.20		

Patient on treatment with drugs which increases the risk of ocular surface lesions						
6.	No	5	55.60	12	50.00	0.081 0.776 (NS)
	Yes	4	44.40	12	50.00	
a. Metformin						
	No	5	55.60	16	66.70	0.349 0.555 (NS)
	Yes	4	44.40	8	33.30	
b. Metoprolol						
	No	6	66.70	19	79.20	0.557 0.456 (NS)
	Yes	3	33.30	5	20.80	
c. Telmisartan						
	No	9	100.00	22	91.70	0.798 0.372 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.00	2	8.30	
d. Aspirin						
	No	8	88.90	23	95.80	0.554 0.457 (NS)
	Yes	1	11.10	1	4.20	
e. Atorvastatin						
	No	9	100.00	23	95.80	0.387 0.534 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.00	1	4.20	
f. Amlodipine						

	No	9	100.00	21	87.50	1.238	0.266 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.00	3	12.50		
White blood cell count							
7.	a. Less than 4000 cells/cu.mm	1	11.10	0	0.00	2.791	0.248 (NS)
	b. 4000-11000 cells/cu.mm	5	55.60	14	58.30		
	c. More than 11000 cells/cu.mm	3	33.30	10	41.70		

p>0.05-non significant (NS).

Table 7 depicts that, clinical variables had not shown statistically significant association of severity of corneal complications in experimental group.

Table 8:Association of severity of corneal complications among mechanically ventilated patients with selected demographic variables in control group. N=33

S.No	Demographic variables	Corneal complications						Chi-square value(X ²)	p-value
		Control group							
		F	No risk (P)	F	Mild (P)	F	Severe (P)		
1.	Age in years							5.354	0.253 (NS)
	a. 41-50 Years	5	62.5	6	35.3	6	75		
	b. 51-60Years	1	12.5	5	29.4	2	25		
	c. Above 60 Years	2	25	6	35.3	0	0.0		
2.	Gender							3.986	0.136 (NS)
	a. Male	6	75	16	94.1	5	62.5		
	b. Female	2	25	1	5.9	3	37.5		

p>0.05-non significant (NS).

Table 8 depicts that, demographic variables had not shown statistically significant association of severity of corneal complications in control group.

Table 9: Association of severity of corneal complications among mechanically ventilated patients with selected clinical variables in control group. N=33

S. No	Clinical Variables	Corneal complications						Chi-square value (X ²)	p-value
		Control group							
		F	No risk (P)	F	Mild (P)	F	Severe (P)		
1.	Body mass index (BMI) in kg/m²								
	a. 18.5-24.9 (Healthy weight)	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0	1.355	0.852 (NS)
	b. 25-29.9 (Overweight)	4	50	8	47.1	5	62.5		
	c. More than 30 (Obesity)	4	50	8	47.1	3	37.5		
2.	Co-morbidities								
	No	5	62.5	10	58.8	6	75	1.395	0.845 (NS)
	Yes	3	37.5	6	35.3	2	25		
	If yes, specify	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0		
	a. Cardiac disease								
	No	5	62.5	14	82.4	7	87.5	1.763	0.414 (NS)
	Yes	3	37.5	3	17.6	1	12.5		
	b. Type II diabetes mellitus								

	No	6	75	13	76.5	6	75	0.01	0.995 (NS)
	Yes	2	25	4	23.5	2	25		
c. Thyroid disorder									
	No	8	100	17	100	8	100	-	-
d. Renal disease									
	No	8	100	16	94.1	8	100	0.971	0.616 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0		
3. Days on ventilator support									
	a. 4-7days	7	87.5	16	94.1	5	62.5	4.288	0.117 (NS)
	b. 8-10days	1	12.5	1	5.9	3	37.5		
4. Glasgow coma scale									
	a. coma	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0	0.971	0.914 (NS)
	b. Semicoma	1	12.5	2	11.8	1	12.5		
	c. Stupor	7	87.5	14	82.4	7	87.5		
5. Diagnosis									
	a. Cardiovascular disease	4	50	9	52.9	1	12.5	9.853	0.275
	b. Respiratory disease	1	12.5	1	5.9	0	0.0		
	c. Neurological disease	3	37.5	6	35.3	4	50		
	d. Multi organ dysfunction syndrome	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	12.5		

	e. Renal disease	0	0.0	1	5.9	2	25		(NS)
6.	Patient on treatment with drugs which increases the risk of ocular surface lesions								
	No	5	62.5	11	64.7	6	75	0.342	0.843 (NS)
	Yes	3	37.5	6	35.3	2	25		
	a. Metformin								
	No	6	75	13	76.5	6	75	0.01	0.995 (NS)
	Yes	2	25	4	23.5	2	25		
	b. Metoprolol								
	No	6	75	15	88.2	7	87.5	0.799	0.671 (NS)
	Yes	2	25	2	11.8	1	12.5		
	c. Telmisartan								
	No	8	100	16	94.1	8	100	0.971	0.616 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0		
	d. Aspirin								
	No	8	100	16	94.1	8	100	0.971	0.616 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0		
	e. Atorvastatin								
	No	8	100	16	94.1	8	100		

	Yes	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0	0.971	0.616 (NS)
f. Amlodipine									
	No	8	100	16	94.1	8	100	0.971	0.616 (NS)
	Yes	0	0.0	1	5.9	0	0.0		
White blood cell count									
7.	a. Less than 4000 cells/cu.mm	2	25	2	11.8	0	0.0	4.71	0.318 (NS)
	b. 4000-11000 cells/cu.mm	3	37.5	10	58.8	7	87.5		
	c. More than 11000 cells/cu.mm	3	37.5	5	29.4	1	12.5		

p>0.05-non significant (NS).

Table 9 depicts that, clinical variables had not shown statistically significant association of severity of corneal complications in control group.

Discussion

Objective:1

Evaluate the effectiveness of comprehensive eye care protocol on corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation.

Friedman test was computed to compare the mean score of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation **within** experimental and control group which shows **highly statistically significant at the level of p<0.001.**

Mann-Whitney test was computed to compare the mean score of post-test severity of corneal complications **between** experimental and control group which shows **statistically significant p=0.057** respectively.

Objective:2

Associate the corneal complications among mechanically ventilated patients with their selected demographic and clinical variables.

The demographic variables namely age, gender and clinical variables did not have any significant association with the corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation. *Hence the stated hypothesis (H₂) that association exists between corneal complications of patients with mechanical ventilation admitted in critical care unit and selected demographic and clinical variables was not accepted.*

Conclusion

It is concluded that prevalence of corneal complications among patients with mechanical ventilation due to improper hygiene and low immune status. So, the adequate eye care is more important for the patient to improve the clinical outcome.

The Statistical evidence proved that the Comprehensive eye care protocol (CECP) was effective, reducing and prevents the chance of corneal complications of patients with mechanical ventilation while comparing the post-test findings of experimental and control group. Hence, the researcher concluded that the Comprehensive eye care protocol (CECP) can be applied for corneal complications to gain a better outcome and well-being.

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